

Research Tools for Digitised Documents Co-design Workshop Report for the HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons

The Australian Research Data Commons

14/04/2025

Version 1.1

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15321171](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15321171)

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	2
THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS	2
THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB	3
OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS	4
THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP	4
CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP	4
NEXT STEPS	10
APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES	11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report summarises responses from the workshop held on 25th March 2025 to co-design an upcoming ARDC infrastructure project that aims to develop tools and workflows to effectively search across corpora with semantic as well as keyword-based search.

This project is part of the Community Data Lab, which fosters the development of tools, datasets and documentation that enable researchers to use data from galleries, libraries, museums, archives and other collections.

From 2022, the ARDC has been making a major investment in digital research infrastructure for humanities, arts, social sciences and Indigenous research data communities. This work has been done in accordance with the 2016 NCRIS Roadmap and Department of Education commissioned studies. The projects undertaken in this area formed an emerging *HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons*.

In late 2023, the ARDC received the largest ever investment in HASS and Indigenous Research Capability. Since early 2024 we have been undergoing a process of co-design to deliver on an expanded HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons, covering existing and new areas of research infrastructure. Co-designing infrastructure investments with the research community and other stakeholders helps the ARDC to create the greatest possible impact. Development of this infrastructure follows the [HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework](#).

THE HASS AND INDIGENOUS RESEARCH DATA COMMONS

The ARDC is planning new investment in digital research infrastructure for HASS (Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences) and Indigenous research data communities, as part of the [HASS and Indigenous Research Data Commons](#) (RDC).

The HASS and Indigenous RDC began with the identification of opportunities to accelerate the impact of HASS and Indigenous research in the [2016 National Research Infrastructure Roadmap](#). The Australian Government Department of Education commissioned scoping studies to identify investment-ready programs, several of which formed the foundational activities of the HASS and Indigenous RDC.

In 2023, the ARDC received its largest-ever investment in HASS research infrastructure and Indigenous research capability. This \$25 million grant, part of the Australian Government's 2023 National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS) Research Infrastructure Investment Plan Funding Round, supplemented by co-investment from national partners, will further establish

long-term, national digital research infrastructure to support HASS and Indigenous research data communities in Australia.

The ARDC is currently delivering infrastructure in six focus areas, some of which builds upon foundational activities delivered during the first phase of the HASS and Indigenous RDC and some of which are new activities designed in collaboration with the research community. These are:

- Improving Indigenous Research Capabilities
- The Language Data Commons of Australia
- Social Science Research Infrastructure Network
- Australian Internet Observatory
- Australian Creative Histories and Futures
- Connections

THE COMMUNITY DATA LAB

The Community Data Lab is an ongoing activity under the Connections focus area of the HASS and Indigenous RDC. Through the Community Data Lab the ARDC seeks to improve researchers' ability to utilise the data made available from galleries, libraries, archives, museums (GLAM) and other collections. This activity provides tools, datasets and guidance that meet needs shared by researchers with different research problems from multiple disciplines. The outputs of the first phase of the Community Data Lab are now available for use by researchers.

During the delivery of this phase, the ARDC developed a set of principles for the design of sustainable HASS infrastructure, which are (in brief):

- A preference for “infrastructure at rest” over infrastructure which requires costly active support
- The separation of data from analytics
- Efficiency and flexibility of platform design
- Reusable code
- Open Source code and Open Access guidance documents

The ARDC is now in the process of developing Phase 2 of the Community Data Lab to expand this suite of data, tools and guidance materials.

OUR CO-DESIGN PROCESS

The ARDC is developing this infrastructure in accordance with the HASS and Indigenous RDC co-design framework (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10516606>). This process is designed to create the greatest impact for research and researchers by co-designing the infrastructure with the people who will benefit from it. Development will follow the stages of Problem Identification, Project Shaping, Project Planning, and Endorsement.

We began Problem Identification in 2024, by calling openly for registrations of interest from partners who might be able to help us to design and deliver projects for the Community Data Lab. We targeted groups at universities that provide research software engineering and data analytics support to HASS researchers, because these groups have strong experience building solutions for researchers and exposure to a range of current researcher needs. We brought potential partners together for a series of roundtable discussions. Through these discussions we identified a set of possible projects which would each serve the needs of researchers from multiple disciplines across multiple research institutions, and which could be developed in line with the principles described above.

The Project Shaping phase was implemented through the open co-design workshop described below. The workshop was advertised through ARDC newsletters, social media channels and other networks. We sought to involve experts in research practice, disciplinary needs and infrastructure provision to better understand the current challenges faced by stakeholders and the outcomes that they hope to see, and to shape potential solutions that could be provided by the new infrastructure.

Project Planning and Endorsement phases will follow - further information is provided in the “Next Steps” section below.

THE PROJECT OPPORTUNITY AND PARTNERSHIP

The proposed project aims to develop tools and workflows to effectively search across corpora with semantic as well as keyword-based search. This project is being developed in partnership with Melbourne Data Analytics Platform (MDAP), The University of Melbourne.

CO-DESIGN WORKSHOP

The co-design workshop was held virtually on 25th March 2025. The workshop was open to all and was attended by 30 participants from 13 organisations. Organisations represented included 6 Australian universities, as well as government organisations, research infrastructure providers and consulting companies.

The workshop aimed to refine our understanding of the challenge, validate the problem statement and its impact, confirm the user base for the proposed solution, and gather feedback on the proposed solution's features.

A/Prof Nic Geard, Dr Daniel Russo-Batterham and Dr Robert Turnbull (Melbourne Data Analytics Platform, The University of Melbourne) presented on the challenge, which was summarised with the following problem statement:

“GLAM organisations often have important information stored on documents attached to collection items (such as labels and supporting paper/card). Digital images of these text-bearing documents can be readily produced but it is a challenge to accurately extract the text and associate it with the appropriate fields. This is a more difficult problem with handwritten labels. GLAM institutions also make available books, newspapers, magazines and more in PDF format, but it is difficult to search and answer research questions across a large corpora of these documents due to variations in layout, content, and OCR quality.”

Participants completed a series of discussion activities in breakout groups, and recorded their input using the Miro online whiteboard tool. Some key themes from the responses are highlighted below - full responses can be found in Appendix 1.

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

Have we described the problem correctly?

- Expanding the problem statement
 - While it talks about PDFs, the process really relates to images saved within PDFs (re-ocring, segmenting, identifying structures etc). So why not talk about processing digitised images more generally rather than PDFs?
 - Would it be clearer to focus the problem statement on extracting the text and/or images etc, and then associating it with labels etc?
 - Linking to the right fields could be expanded - semantically identifying content
 - Is recognition of image components in scope?
- Digitisation levels and definition
 - The term digitised is far too general. We need a precisely-defined set of levels to denote the degree of digitisation: from raw scanned imagery through to vetted, rich OCR text. A useful analogue might be the processing levels used to classify Earth Observation data (initially developed by NASA)
- Tools and workflow considerations

- While creation of digital images may be easy, there is a huge amount of work in preparing materials for digitisation that might need to be considered as part of the problem. Integration into current digitisation initiatives might be valuable
- If LLMs are used here, need to incorporate standardised, good ways of creating prompts to identify data structures - guidance and templates here would be useful
- Some standard tools struggle with tabular data - so tools for handling this kind of data would be useful
- Need accessible workflows for correcting OCR outputs
- Considerations relating to search, discovery and metadata
 - Need to pre-define where the scans/metadata are going before they are processed - re-usable by whom, how?
 - If this is about discoverability, some kind of federated metasearch across institutions would be good
- Other comments/questions
 - Does this suggest working with existing digitised collections with inadequate metadata, search due to unreadability would be a better starting point?

Who is this problem important to?

- Collection managers
- Archivists
- Researchers, including researchers in AI, Data Science, NLP and OCR.
- Government and NGOs
- General public

Would addressing this problem be valuable (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)

- Support for historical and multilingual text analysis
 - OCR-ing non-English texts, then translating them and analysing them alongside related English texts
 - Early modern text analysis with multiple languages such as Latin, English, German, French etc
 - Having full text of different corpuses can make transnational historical research much easier (and trans-disciplinary) research
- Enhanced access and discoverability
 - It could allow a wider audience to know about or even read old and ancient texts and make it easier to search through them
 - Making documents more accessible - very valuable and important
 - Surfacing hidden information - for example rare biodiversity collections
- Improved research and metadata management
 - Linking information - entities within text could be linked to other sources of information
- Tools, workflows and research infrastructure

- It would be good if these sorts of tools could be packaged as plugins for existing tools used to manage content from GLAM collections -- eg Omeka, Zotero, Tropy
- The value will be contingent on providing the data in a format and in an interface that meets the needs of researchers and collection managers
- Use of AI and LLMs
 - Using LLM like Deep Seek for OCR on historical records can give great results
 - If AI is now good enough to handle handwritten manuscripts and generate metadata that would be very useful
- Computational and NLP-enabled analysis
 - Will be very useful for text analysis and NLP tasks
 - Capturing both structure and content of historical documents allows new forms of computational analysis
 - Time saver -allow time for traditional analysis as well as enabling computational analysis

Activity 2: Do you have specific examples of textual documents that are difficult to digitise due to format, layout and text quality?

- Handwritten text and annotation challenges
 - In humanities, OCR for handwritten manuscripts and being able to work with that has been a constant desire.
 - Cursive handwriting especially for different scripts and non-english characters (or scribbles?)
 - Documents which include a variety of handwritten historical units such as currency, distances, weights which are abbreviated in a number of ways. Eg: pounds/shillings/pence
- Multilingual and non-latin script
 - Multilingual OCR doesn't handle non Latin text, and right to left text
 - non english language documents and older forms of english
- Complex document structure and layout
 - Forms whose layouts change over time, that include a combination of printed and handwritten text, and can also include things like photos, stamps, and handwritten annotations in the margins and across the other content
 - Printed directories, such as Post Office directories, that have tiny text, multiple columns, and little space between columns. For full value need both the page/column/line structure, but also the broader context -- e.g. may be part of a suburb listing, but the suburb heading is on an earlier page.
 - Documents where formatting is significant - ie. bold, italic characters
- Marginalia
 - Paratext with notes in margins that may link documents together
- Specific examples

- NZ colonial Hansard! Great to see that being solved
- Births deaths and marriages from 19th century and linking people historically
- church records in 16-18th century Italy.
- Fragile, bound and physical format constraints
 - Old fragile bindings of books that can't be opened widely enough to digitise.
 - Fabric sample books - women recording what they sewed over their lifetimes
 - Digitising ancient books without destroying them can be tough. But T-rays technology was improving (Terahertz non-destructive scanning)
- Other considerations raised
 - Maintaining links among materials extracted from a single object is essential and difficult
 - Be careful not to separate the documents from the purposes: different goals will require different approaches.

Activity 3: How would you currently approach analysing low quality text records (e.g. handwritten, scanned, or generated by optical character recognition (OCR))? What methods would you use and what are their limitations?

- Manual and human-centered approaches
 - Manually typing out key points or entire text
 - Finding other works by same authors
- Commercial and AI powered tools
 - Microsoft Document Intelligence, and AWS Textract as well as Transkribus, with additional Python (to fix columns, remove errant page artefacts etc) when needed.
 - Take the OCR'd text and give it to a commercial to analyse with an LLM
 - Transkribus for extracting print and handwritten text. Has an API for embedding in pipelines
- Community
 - Zooniverse and DigiVol for crowdsourcing transcription/correction of digitised documents
 - Teams of very passionate volunteers
- Workflow design and validation
 - Workflow is critical in validating OCR results
 - Workflows need to incorporate human validation particularly from experts
 - Retention of images of the content is essential to enable downstream quality control
- Software
 - Openrefine for structuring and cleaning extracted tabular data
 - When dealing with some PDFs with bad OCR, I extracted the images and ran them through Tesseract
 - Tropy (<https://trophy.org>)

Activity 4: How would you like to interact with and process textual corpora, including capabilities that are not currently possible (e.g., searching, correction, defining bespoke vocabularies)? Be as specific as possible and give examples.

- Search
 - API access to search results
 - Keyword searching through handwritten texts
 - Search with feedback on OCR quality to help understand the completeness of results
 - Ability to navigate and view across the hierarchy of collection / volume / page / paragraph / line from search results to understand context
- Creating a knowledge graph
- Visualisation and analysis
 - Being able to create visualisations from convention debates, on who is saying what on a particular topic
 - Computational analysis of large corpora of digital records
 - Automatic creation of facets for structured text to allow for quick analysis, overviews, and guided navigation
- Correction, annotation and version tracking
 - Tracking version histories and notes from correctors
- Digitisation and OCR challenges
 - Most textual items not born digital will need to remain linked to their respective source scans
 - Distinguishing distinct hands in handwritten documents
 - How do you access the ocr'd text and search it?
- Text enrichment and semantic linking
 - A primary limitation of text analytics approaches is the assumption that documents are a single text field - it's great that this is starting from structure
 - Linking semantic entities within text to their source of truth eg scientific names, people, places, events <https://www.wikidata.org/> is a useful source
 - Automatically NER on recorded interviews
 - For historical text perform name entity recognition, automatically link entity to geo spatial information, perform geospatial or timeline mapping; automatically link entity to other entities
- Custom vocabularies and historical information
 - If a system depends on a vocab of any kind (eg: placenames, keywords), I need to be able to extend it, adding my own set of terms for my study
 - Dealing with historic information. Not assuming modern places, peoples names. Especially dates. Many systems and codes cannot handle dates beyond some threshold, whether it's before 1900, or years with less than 4 digits or, BC dates.

NEXT STEPS

The ARDC has worked with the potential project team to develop a draft project plan, released for public feedback alongside the publication of this report. Feedback submissions will close end of day Friday 23 May. To submit feedback on project plans please use the form on the ARDC website. All feedback will be collated and responded to in a published report, alongside an updated project plan taking into account this feedback wherever possible. Work on this project is planned to commence in July 2025.

The development of the resulting infrastructure will involve ongoing public testing and consultation - please make sure you are signed up to the HASS and I newsletter so that you receive notifications about upcoming opportunities to be involved.

If you have any other comments or questions about this process please contact us at hassi.codesign@ardc.edu.au with the subject line 'Digitised Documents'.

APPENDIX 1: WORKSHOP RESPONSES

Full text of workshop responses

Activity 1: Understanding the problem

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Have we described the problem correctly?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Yes good description. What kind of GLAM institutions? ● Problem for institutional collections is that it's too big to do manually, so AI is a necessary solution. However, it has a high error rate. As a user this is acceptable, because it's great to find most things, when before I couldn't, so long as I know I'm probably not finding all things, and some are wrong. So need to a) figure out how to inform user of error, b) decide whether to do human corrections, c) figure out how to identify and prioritise what needs correction, data cleaning, other types of human intervention and maintenance, c) how to resource and staff all this activity. The people and skills are an essential part of the new 'system. ● Rather than focusing on the rather limited case of cards and labels, could this be generalised to look at a broader range of structured formats such as forms, ledgers, tables etc. There are a number of such types of documents where the structure is as important as the content. +1 ● While it talks about PDFs, the process really relates to images saved within PDFs (re-ocring, segmenting, identifying structures etc). So why not talk about processing digitised images more generally rather than PDFs? +1 ● If LLMs are used here, need to incorporate standardised, good ways of creating prompts to identify data structures - guidance and templates here would be useful ● Need to pre-define where the scans/metadata are going before they are processed - re-usable by whom, how? ● Would it clearer to focus the problem statement on extracting the text and/or images etc, and then associating it with labels etc? ● Yes but some of the problems relate to the broader workflows ● The term digitised is far too general. We need a precisely-defined set of levels to denote the degree of digitisation: from raw scanned imagery through to vetted, rich OCR text. A useful analogue might be the processing levels used to classify Earth Observation data (initially developed by NASA) ● If this is about discoverability, some kind of federated metasearch across institutions would be good. (in terms of 'is this the right question?') ● While creation of digital images may be easy, there is a huge amount of work in preparing materials for digitisation, that might need to be considered as part of the problem. Integration into current digitisation initiatives might be valuable. +1 ● Need to define levels of digitisation of documents (e.g., image, metadata, OCR) ● Use will be determined by how accessible the tools will be to

	<p>researchers, requiring an intuitive interface that is easy and quick to use.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researcher as ground truth. Need accessible workflows for correcting OCR outputs. ● Maybe another big issue is streamlining the process of taking images of all these texts (e.g. a ios/android app)? Not sure how many handwritten texts have been properly digitised? It's a long process after all ● Linking to the right fields could be expanded - semantically identifying content ● PDF is more of a wrapper which can encapsulate different formats of information for display, e.g. scanned bitmaps vs formatted text. There is no single way of accessing PDF content in a standard way. ● Dealing with sensitive data that is not known to be sensitive until item is digitised ● Big thumbs up ● But also need to be careful about limits of what is solved and where situation/local context adaption is necessary ● Does this suggest working with existing digitised collections with inadequate metadata, search due to unreadability would be a better starting point? ● Not just text - also for identifying things in images ● some standard tools struggle with tabular data - so tools for handling this kind of data would be useful ● Need to be flexible enough for many different uses ● Is recognition of image components in scope
--	--

QUESTION	RESPONSES
Who is the problem important to?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Data collections with the capacity/capability to reprocess existing archives into (additional) more useable formats ● Collection managers including many at UoM who are involved in the digitisation of the documents. Increasing the capture of data for CMS is very valuable. ● Researchers in AI, Data Science, NLP, and even OCR itself. Great data to train models on (e.g. to study old/dead languages) ● Lots of major collections internationally are generating annotated IIIF manifests as an esport format. ● PDF proposition seems generic and scalable. ● Anyone looking at old documents ● Collection managers - to enable better management of collections where metadata is in legacy control documents ● archives with historical data in tabular formats like census data ● Archivists would benefit greatly from standard formats and methods ● research on historical text ● Nick Carr from Currawong handwritten death certificates from the 19th century ● There would be a large group of (currently) unidentifiable researchers who may be interested, if it was a simple matter to see what was

	<p>there.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Researchers interested in Births deaths and mariages and linking people historically ● historians - useful for getting and categorising text - what something is on a page ● Collection managers providing the digital content. They hold ultimate responsibility for making the digital content accessible for research use. ● Anyone digitising anything ● people in libraries, governments, ngos etc ● Data producers/ digitisation providers.. making the source data more suitable for additional data extraction/gathering ● Might be worth reaching out similar initiates in federal public sector ● Large commercial ventures who would love this data for free ● Sophisticated researcher workflows UX required for emendation of AI results ● Generate outputs as annotated IIIF. Take advantage of exiting workflow tooling (Glycerine) to support researcher in correcting pipeline results. ● Directly relevant to working with pre-digital language materials - (see https://nyingarn.net/),https://nyingarn.net/, https://nyingarn.net/ ● useful for scrapbooks - identifying items on a page; identifying the sections of texts
--	--

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>Would addressing this problem be valuable? (what would be enabled if we solved this problem?)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OCR-ing non-English texts, then translating them and analysing them alongside related English texts. ● early modern text analysis with multiple languages such as Latin, English, German, French etc ● Using LLM's like Deep Seek for OCR on historical records can give great results ● It could allow a wider audience to know about or even read old and ancient texts. And make it easier to search through them ● Tech for OCR are/will change rapidly. Researchers need workflows to mediate results, ● It would be good if these sort of tools could be packaged as plugins for existing tools used to manage content from GLAM collections -- eg Omeka, Zotero, Tropy. ● will be very useful for text analysis and NLP tasks ● The value will be contingent on providing the data in a format and in an interface that meets the needs of researchers and collection managers. ● Having full text of different corpuses can make transnational historical research much easier (and trans-disciplinary) research. ● Use of Glycerine as a researcher Workbench to call AI pipelines and provide workflows for researchers to accept/reject results . Generate outputs as annotated IIIF.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● historical text analysis for 15-19th centuries ● If AI is now good enough to handle handwritten manuscripts and generate metadata that would be very useful. ● Capturing both structure and content of historical documents allows new forms of computational analysis ● surfacing hidden information - for example rare biodiversity collections ● Extracting data is more relevant for researchers, collection managers and those who research historical material ● Supporting manual + hybrid workflows also important ● A wide range of domains would be enabled to see if there are things of interest in these documents (i.e. any topic that is covered in the documents could then be traceable to researchers interested in that topic) ● Linking information - entities within text could be linked to other sources of information ● Many uses, but LLM's will need to be trained per case to ensure useful results ● time saver -allow time for traditional analysis as well as enabling computational analysis ● Yes, I'm accumulating more and more historical manuscripts, pdfs, images etc, and losing track of what is what, and which docs are relevant to which of hundreds of historical events, people, topics, etc. So I'd need to be able to tell the AI to look for particular topics and create metadata for my specific research interest. Would be good if this didn't just generated metadata, but interface has filter of the metadata, and more importantly, interactive search of the materials, as I come up with new questions on the spot. Also for audio and video, some streamlining of process of creating AI transcript, into metadata generation. ● It will depend on providing the outputs into the data standards across research fields. ● making documents more accessible - very valuable and important ● Potentially extending the life of the OCRd information - becoming re-usable ● Need to also consider simpler solutions where scale is not as great an issue for manual data extraction. Quicker to customise a solution to specific needs with less overheads. ● really shaky scans into deep seek or chatgpt which understood the structures ● where something is on a page can be as important in historical research - big help with that
--	--

Activity 2

QUESTION	RESPONSES
Do you have specific examples of textual	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Forms whose layouts change over time, that include a combination of printed and handwritten text, and can also include things like photos,

<p>documents that are difficult to digitise due to format, layout and text quality?</p>	<p>stamps, and handwritten annotations in the margins and across the other content.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● annotating transcription to source image is critical in handwritten documents ● Pages from large bound volumes such as ledgers that include print and handwritten text arranged in columns and rows, including both letters, number and currency values. The column and row headings can change over time, as can the layout of the page, the fonts, the paper etc. ● Cursive handwriting especially for different scripts and non-english characters (or scribbles?) ● Documents with text running in multiple directions. ● Born digital documents that have a heavy design component ● Page images from tightly bound volumes where the content of the left-hand column are partially obscured. ● Old structured data, such as Mission records, and the colonial census often has complex structures, such as headings, subheadings covering multicells etc. Or formatting such as bold italics having meaning. AI and automated tools often are very glitchy handling this. Even when digitisation reflects the original very well, such as the Colonial Census, the structure is so complex and inconsistent it's still not very useful for computation, and it still needs to be translated to a flat and consistent structure manually, which is very time consuming. ● historical text from 15-19th centuries with multiple languages such as Latin, English, German, French... ● Old fragile bindings of books that can't be opened widely enough to digitise. ● Documents where formatting is significant - ie. bold, italic characters ● Multilingual OCR doesn't handle non Latin text, and right to left text. ● handwriting on the historical manuscripts ● In humanities, OCR for handwritten manuscripts and being able to work with that has been a constant desire. ● non english language documents and older forms of english ● Non-English based text ● Non Romanic characters ● Handwritten language documentation (word lists/vocabularies) - for example: http://www.bates.org.au/, http://www.bates.org.au/, </p> ● Philology requires annotation of the source image as ground truth ● Glass slides ● Documents which include a variety of handwritten historical units such as currency, distances, weights which are abbreviated in a number of ways. Eg: pounds/shillings/pence ● NZ colonial Hansard! Great to see that being solved. ● Researchers interested in Births deaths and marriages from 19th century and linking people historically ● Printed directories, such as Post Office directories, that have tiny text, multiple columns, and little space between columns. For full value need both the page/column/line structure, but also the broader context -- eg may be part of a suburb listing, but the suburb heading is on an earlier page.
---	--

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● physical documents (requires access to scanners and people with time) ● Fabric sample books - women recording what they sewed over their lifetimes ● Rebound items e.g. journals, serial publications ● Digitising ancient books without destroying them can be tough. But T-rays technology was improving (Terahertz non-destructive scanning) ● church records in 16-18th century Italy. ● scrapbooks, collections of historical ephemera ● Terahertz scanning (scanning a book without opening it) ● Need to consider research objectives. Does text need to be annotated on the source images? ● Family documents like family bibles and cookbooks ● scrapbooks/ consular books/ political ephemera ● Marginalia in editions ● maintaining links among materials extracted from a single object is essential and difficult ● Expand the notion of document to be multi-modal ● Paratext with notes in margins that may link documents together etc. ● Be careful not to separate the documents from the purposes: different goals will require different approaches.
--	--

Activity 3

QUESTION	RESPONSES
How would you currently approach analysing low quality text records (e.g. handwritten, scanned, or generated by optical character recognition (OCR))? What methods would you use and what are their limitations?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Microsoft Document Intelligence, and AWS Textract as well as Transkribus, with additional Python (to fix columns, remove errant page artefacts etc) when needed. ● Use commercial large language model ● Challenge with sensitive data ● Workflow is critical in validating OCR results. ● Openrefine for structuring and cleaning extracted tabular data ● Manually typing out key points or entire text ● Amazon Mechanical Turk ● Finding other works by same authors ● Not just to find another copy scanned, but to decode structure/meaning ● humans! ● Teams of very passionate volunteers ● digitised handwritten documents - manually typing out (either the whole document or key points) - very expensive time wise ● Manual (human) transcription from images ● Look for other samples of handwriting by the same author (in order to decipher a text) ● Verification of ocr by human - eg wikisource uses OCR with one person correcting and another person verifying before it is made live. https://en.wikisource.org/,https://en.wikisource.org/,

	<p>https://en.wikisource.org/</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Take the OCR'd text and give it to a commercial to an LLM ● ocr and language model, fine tuning, inferencing ● Zooniverse and DigiVol for crowdsourcing transcription / correction of digitised documents. ● Doesn't separate handwriting notes and the actual manuscript ● Limitation - access to high quality scanners ● Custom computer vision tools for segmentation / identifying structures. ● Transkribus for extracting print and handwritten text. Has an API for embedding in pipelines. ● Human involvement in error-checking is clearly valuable - how can it be optimised? to enable human & AI resources to efficiently complement one another. ● Using Apple live text with Filemaker Pro to provide a combination of image display and text analysis (looking for the text of a physical stamp added to some index cards). Provided a mix of automated and manual inspection/transcription that was easily customised to the task. ● When dealing with some PDFs with bad OCR, I extracted the images and ran them through Tesseract. ● I would just limit what I want to use to a direct quote and type it out. If it's that bad it's easier just to type the whole thing, than correct bad OCR. ● BTW I would only use something that is free, and that enables me to get all work I put in, out again in a standard format. I can't afford to speculatively pay for stuff without being sure of it, and won't be locked into a subscription. This is even if I know something might be better than the free version., It's useless if I can't keep my work independently, or use the data in other systems. ● Name entity recognition doesn't perform ver well with very old historical text ● Use Trophy https://trophy.org/,https://trophy.org/, https://trophy.org/ ● Trophy: https://trophy.org/,https://trophy.org/, https://trophy.org/ ● Vetting and scoring of quality of results. ● retention of images of the content is essential to enable downstream quality control ● Not used - but maybe worth prototyping what biologists do - collaboratively shared info grabbed ● Preserving a granular link to the source is critical in validating results. ● quality assessment of ocr content in a standard way (quantified with parameters) ● Workflows need to incorporate human validation particularly from experts ● Use own phone?
--	---

Activity 4

QUESTION	RESPONSES
<p>How would you like to interact with and process textual corpora, including capabilities that are not currently possible (for example, searching, correction, defining bespoke vocabularies, etc)? Be as specific as possible and give examples.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Having historically (and nationally / culturally) appropriate word embeddings for development of vector databases. Or will more powerful models render tis unnecessary in the future? ● Assuming we got perfect data and a large corpora: Knowledge Graphs and see how these corpus connect to each other would be amazing! E.g. a book author spoke about another author, being able to link that sentence to the other author or book (i.e. click on the link to see their work or whatever was quoted) would be great! ● Tracking *annotations* as opposed to simple corrections ● Purpose of use essential before extraction - where will it go finally, how will it be used and analysed? ● Incorporating additional data extraction/ text preparation into digitisation workflows and archive preparation/management ● Visualisations of who was saying what in old Hansard ● Tracking version histories and notes from correctors ● API access to search results ● Correcting- need easy way to fix ● Platforms like some large vendors have, where you can select a template / model type for your type of document, upload the documents (or point to an online source), and press go - text / json output is produced that you can wrangle yourself. ● Keyword searching through handwritten texts ● Deriving meaning and connections across time and changes in vocabulary ● import text into existing databases of archive material ● Search ● Tracking the version history of corrections, for provenance ● Creating a knowledge graph ● Distinguishing distinct hands in handwritten documents ● computational analysis of large corpora of digital records ● visualisation of who was saying what ● If a system depends on a vocab of any kind (eg: placenames, keywords), I need to be able to extend it, adding my own set of terms for my study. ● Above all, OCR handwritten texts. Then I can search them etc.. Also, handle and correct scanned structured data like columns and tables. ● Automatically NER on recorded interviews, AV. ● Ability to download search results in a structured format, eg CSV. ● build networks (e.g. family trees via births deaths marriages) ● knowledge graph ● For historical text perform name entity recognition, automatically link entity to geo spatial information, perform geospatial or timeline mapping; automatically link entity to other entities

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● downstream formatting to meet research standard formats (e.g. DwC) is essential for downstream scalability an ● Ability to navigate and view across the hierarchy of collection / volume / page / paragraph / line from search results to understand context. ● Dealing with historic information. Not assuming modern places, peoples names. Especially dates. Many systems and codes cannot handle dates beyond some threshold, whether its before 1900, or years with less than 4 digits or, BC dates. ● Automatically map places in text. Autodetect coordinates in text. Autodetect dates in text. Interface to relate dates, coordinates, placenames events, etc that were detected in text. Tool/interface to relate these across texts and in other databases, and media. ● being able to create visualisations from convention debates, on who is saying what on a particular topic ● IIIF will support high quality images ● How do you access the ocr'd text and search it? ● perform sentiment analysis, question and answer, network analysis, topic model and linking entity on historical documents. ● Search with feedback on OCR quality to help understand the completeness of results. ● Automatic creation of facets for structured text to allow for quick analysis, overviews, and guided navigation. ● A primary limitation of text analytics approaches is the assumption that documents are a single text field - it's great that this is starting from structure. +1 ● Most textual items not born digital will need to remain linked to their respective source scans. ● Linking semantic entities within text to their source of truth eg scientific names, people, places, events https://www.wikidata.org/ is a useful source, https://www.wikidata.org/, https://www.wikidata.org/
--	--